

The Benefits of a Silvopastoral Pig System and the Supports Available in Ireland

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Silvopastoral pig system (Photo: Teagasc)
Pigs in a recently established silvopastoral system, with
protected tree in the background

A silvopastoral pig system combines trees, forage, and pigs to create a sustainable, productive farm. Pigs benefit from shade in summer and shelter in winter, while their rooting aerates soil, reducing ploughing. Rotational grazing prevents over-disturbance, boosting pasture productivity by 10–20% and enhancing soil fertility through manure recycling.

This system provides environmental and economic benefits. Trees reduce nitrate leaching by 30%, stabilize soil, and improve water absorption. They also enhance biodiversity by creating wildlife habitats. Premium pork can sell for 30% more, while oak acorns, produced during a mast year, can cut feed costs by 40% in autumn. Integrating livestock, timber, and forage increases farm efficiency.

Pigs can be introduced into existing fruit and nut orchards, where they will consume fallen fruit, nuts, and leaves, lowering feed costs and controlling pests and weeds. Their manure fertilizes the soil. Suitable trees include oak, hazel, walnut, mulberry, sweet chestnut, apple, and pear, which provide seasonal food. Young trees need 4–5 years of protection using tree guards, fencing, or electric barriers. Kunekune pigs, a grazing breed, cause less tree damage than other pigs.

Ireland's Forest Type 8 – Agroforestry scheme supports tree planting with food production. Eligible land must be at least 0.5 hectares, with a minimum width of 20 meters and at least 400 trees per hectare. Approved species include oak, sycamore, and cherry, with others considered. Once converted, land is classified as forest under the Forestry Act 2014. Farmers can receive €8,555 per hectare (excluding fencing) and an annual payment of €975 per hectare for 10 years, available to both farmers and non-farmers.

By integrating pork, timber, and forage, a silvopastoral pig system reduce costs, boost income, and improve soil health. With proper management, this sustainable system benefits farmers and the environment long-term.

References

Department of Agriculture, Food & the Marine (2024). Afforestation Scheme 2023-2027 Document. Available at <https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/crops/forestry/grants/Afforestation-Scheme-2023-2027-04-2024.pdf>

Dundalk Institute of Technology Research. (2020). Silvopasture: A sustainable method to improve soil quality and productivity on farms in the North-West region of Ireland. <https://eprints.dkit.ie/id/eprint/770/>

Irish Agroforestry Forum. (2023). Silvopasture with pigs: A sustainable approach to pig farming in Ireland. Available at <https://www.irishagroforestry.ie>

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